

COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF CONTAMINANT TRANSPORT UNDER NONLINEAR BIODEGRADATION AND PHYSICAL SORPTION PROCESSES IN A SATURATED POROUS MEDIUM

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to develop a computational modelling for a multiple species contaminant transport under nonlinear biodegradation and physical sorption processes in a saturated porous medium, which characterizes a scenario of subsurface contamination by organic contaminants. Sorption in nonlinear equilibrium and non-equilibrium conditions are incorporated upon the model setting as Freundlich type. Moreover, aerobic biodegradation is modelled through the multiplicative Monod kinetic. Mathematically, the problem is given by a nonlinear advection-diffusion-reaction partial differential system coupled by the reaction terms, associated with the biodegradation process. A new operator-splitting approach is proposed for treating in a sequential fashion the convective-diffusive and reactive terms. A predictor-multi corrector algorithm with Newton-Raphson and stabilized finite element (SUPG) methods are used in the time and spatial discretizations, respectively. Numerical results illustrate the good applicability and the effectiveness of the present approach, corroborating the well-known observation that to better predict contamination scenarios the nonlinear physical and biological processes should be inserted in the model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many numerical attempts based on fully coupled approaches, such as those introduced in the works of Celia and Kindred [1989], Couto and Malta [2006], Bell and Binning [2004], Farthing et al. [2005] and Kanney et al. [2003b], or operator splitting methodologies, introduced by Couto and Malta [2005], Kanney et al. [2003a], Kacur et al. [2005], Odencrantz [1991] and Remesíková [2005], have been shown to solve contaminant transport problems under biological and physical processes. Most of these papers deal with these processes in a separately way, and none of them simulates all the nonlinear sorption conditions combined with nonlinear biodegradation process together. In a submitted paper [Couto and Malta, 2006], we proposed a fully coupled numerical model to study a multiple species diffusive-convective transport problem under a nonlinear minimum-rate Monod biodegradation process and nonlinear sorption in equilibrium mode. The computational results were performed to different Freundlich isotherm coefficients and exponents showing

the retardation effects of the linear and nonlinear sorption conditions upon the contaminant transport combined with and without biodegradation process. Following these ideas, our main contribution here focus on the introduction of both nonlinear sorption conditions combined with multiplicative Monod biodegradation kinetic, for numerically solving more realistic contamination scenarios. A new operator-splitting methodology is proposed to study this strong nonlinear problem. This operator-splitting procedure is ideal for parallel computation, for large multidimensional problems with multiple species and, finally, the most important in our case, for treating in a fashion way different types of biodegradation kinetics and sorption conditions. We will introduce in a forthcoming paper, an extension of this numerical methodology in order to understand the influence of taking different types of biodegradation kinetics together with the sorption effects on the multiple species contaminant transport problems in two dimension.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

We study a mathematical model which considers a multiple species diffusive-convective contaminant transport system with mass transfer between a fluid phase and a solid phase, and biodegradation reactions in a porous medium. This model is given by a system of equation involving two variables in the fluid phase, namely, the contaminant concentration (electron donor), C_1 , and the reaction oxidant agent (oxygen) or electron acceptor, C_2 . We also include the contaminant solid phase concentration S_1 . The equation for the bacterial growth is assumed with the bacterial biomass fixed in the solid grain is denoted by b_1 . Then, the model equations are written as

$$\frac{\partial F(C_1)}{\partial t} + V \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial x} - D \frac{\partial^2 C_1}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial t} + \alpha_3 R_1(C_1, C_2, b_1) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial S_1}{\partial t} = \alpha_2 K (\Psi(C_1) - S_1), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} + V \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial x} - D \frac{\partial^2 C_2}{\partial x^2} + \alpha_4 R_2(C_1, C_2, b_1) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial b_1}{\partial t} = \alpha_5 R_3(C_1, C_2, b_1), \quad (4)$$

for all $x \in (0, L)$ and $t > 0$. We impose usual boundary conditions for the contaminant, $C_1(0, t) = \bar{C}_1$ and $\frac{\partial C_1(L, t)}{\partial x} = 0$, and for the electron donor, $C_2(0, t) = \bar{C}_2$ and $\frac{\partial C_2(L, t)}{\partial x} = 0$. Besides, initial conditions are taking as $C_1(x, 0) = C_1^0$, $S_1(x, 0) = \Psi(C_1^0)$, $C_2(x, 0) = C_2^0$ and $b_1(x, 0) = b_1^0$. All these variables are given constants.

In equations (1)-(4), $V > 0$ and $D > 0$ are the velocity and diffusion coefficients. Functions $R_1(\cdot)$, $R_2(\cdot)$ and $R_3(\cdot)$ represent the reaction terms, depending on the biodegradation kinetic choice. Moreover, $F(C_1) = C_1 + \alpha_1 \Phi(C_1)$ is a non-linear function related to the equilibrium isotherm $\Phi(\cdot)$. The non-equilibrium isotherm is denoted by $\Psi(\cdot)$, and $K > 0$ is the reaction rate. Constants α_i , $i = 1, \dots, 5$, are put equal to 1.0 or 0.0 if the associated phenomenon is activated or not. Namely, α_1 is related with sorption in equilibrium mode, α_2 with sorption in non-equilibrium mode and, α_i , $i = 3, 4, 5$ with the biodegradation kinetic.

In this work we choose Freundlich isotherms for modelling both equilibrium and non-equilibrium sorption conditions, that is, $\Phi(C_1) = \Psi(C_1) = K_0 C_1^p$ with exponent p a

measure of the sorption intensity. For the linear case ($p = 1$), the sorption capacity coefficient K_0 is denoted by K_d and it is called distribution coefficient or partition coefficient [?]. One of the most important goal in this work is to assume $p \neq 1$, becoming function $F(C_1)$ strongly non-linear. In particular, we apply the multiplicative Monod expression [Celia et al. 1989, Odencrantz, 1991], with the reaction terms define in the following form:

$$R_1(C_1, C_2, b_1) = b_1 V_m \left(\frac{C_1}{K_h^1(C_1) + C_1} \right) \left(\frac{C_2}{K_h^1(C_2) + C_2} \right), \quad (5)$$

$$R_2(C_1, C_2, b_1) = \frac{Y_{C_1}}{Y_{C_2}} R_1(C_1, C_2, b_1), \quad (6)$$

$$R_3(C_1, C_2, b_1) = Y_{C_1} R_1(C_1, C_2, b_1) - m(b_1 - b_1^0), \quad (7)$$

where V_m is the asymptotic maximum uptake rate of contaminant utilization, $K_h^1(C_1)$ and $K_h^1(C_2)$ are the half-saturation constants for the electron donor (contaminant) and the electron acceptor (oxygen). In addition, Y_{C_1} and Y_{C_2} are the cell yield coefficients, m represents the cell decay coefficient and, finally, b_1^0 is the initial biomass concentration.

3. THE NEW OPERATOR SPLITTING PROCEDURE

In this section we explain in details a new numerical scheme proposed to solve the mathematical model presented in section 2. This methodology is based on the ideas introduced in a very recent operator splitting approach given by Kacur et al. [2005] and the work developed by Odencrantz [1991]. Our main contribution focus on the introduction of both nonlinear sorption conditions combined with nonlinear multiplicative biodegradation kinetic. System (1)-(4) is broken up into two parts, namely: the non-reactive solute transport part (including the equilibrium sorption term) and the reactive part (corresponding the biodegradation kinetic and sorption in non-equilibrium mode). In this way, system (1)-(4) yields:

$$\frac{\partial F(C_1)}{\partial t} + V \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial x} - D \frac{\partial^2 C_1}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial F(C_1)}{\partial t} + \alpha_2 \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial t} + \alpha_3 R_1(C_1, C_2, b_1) = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial S_1}{\partial t} = K(\Psi(C_1) - S_1), \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} + V \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial x} - D \frac{\partial^2 C_2}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_2}{\partial t} + \alpha_4 R_2(C_1, C_2, b_1) = 0, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial b_1}{\partial t} = \alpha_5 R_3(C_1, C_2, b_1). \quad (13)$$

In the following we describe the operator splitting algorithm, first presenting a temporal discretization for the interval $I = [0, T]$, where T is the final time. Let $0 = t^0 < t^1 < t^2 < \dots < t^N = T$ be the time discretization, such that $I_n \equiv (t^{n-1}, t^n)$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, is a

partition of I . In this work, the time is uniformly divided and the time step is given by $\Delta t = t^n - t^{n-1}$ with $N = T/\Delta t$. The main idea of the algorithm is treat system (8)-(13) in two stages. In the first stage, we consider that an approximate solution of system (8)-(13) is known at time t^{n-1} , and then the non-reactive diffusive-convective equations (8) and (11) are evaluated over the discrete interval I_n . To numerically solve these nonlinear diffusive-convective transport equations we employ a predictor-multi corrector algorithm with a Newton-Raphson method in the time discretization. The stabilized SUPG (Streamline Upwind Petrov-Galerkin) finite element method [Brooks and Hughes, 1982] is used in the spatial approximation to consistently introduce an additional stability term in the upwind direction, preventing non-physical oscillations in convection dominant problems [Coutinho et al., 2004]. In the second stage, we locally solve the reaction equations (9), (10), (12) and (13) over I_n , taking into account the solution of the first stage as the initial condition and using a fourth-order Runge-Kutta integration scheme, which is fifth-order accurate in time. The solution of this second stage is the solution for all system at time $t^n \in I_n$. In both stages, equations (8) and (9) become nonlinear if $p \neq 1$. Moreover, when $0 < p < 1$ we have $F'(0) = \infty!$ To circumventing these anomalies, we replace $F'(C_1)$ to $\tilde{F}'(C_1)$, establishing a small parameter ϵ , such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}'(C_1) &:= F'(C_1), \text{ se } C_1 \geq \epsilon \\ &F'(\epsilon), \text{ se } C_1 < \epsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We observe that this operator splitting procedure is very suitable for treating different types of sorption and biodegradation processes.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

To analyze sorption effects on the contaminant transport under biodegradation process, we present here some computational simulations obtained by the operator splitting methodology introduced in the last section. Figures (1)-(4) show the concentration curves for the three species involved, namely, the electron donor (C_1), the acceptor donor (C_2) and the biomass (b_1) in a contamination scenario with the biodegradation kinetic given by equations (5)-(7). In all studied cases, the computational domain has $6m$, the mesh size and time interval are $\Delta x = 0.06m$ and $\Delta t = 0.1 \text{ day}$, respectively, and the Freundlich isotherm parameters is $K_0 = 2.0$. To allow some comparisons among the simulation results, we are considering the biodegradation kinetic values the same as in [Odenrantz, 1991], that is: $V_m = 0.42 \text{ day}^{-1}$, $K_h^1(C_1) = 0.218 \text{ mg/L}$, $K_h^1(C_2) = 0.146 \text{ mg/L}$, $Y_{C_1} = 0.678$, $Y_{C_2} = 0.983$, $m = 0.07 \text{ day}^{-1}$ e $b_1^0 = 0.427 \text{ mg/L}$. The plumes are exhibited at eight different days, namely: 5, 15, 25, 35, 45, 55, 65 and 75 days. The velocity and diffusive values are taken as $V = 0.1 \text{ m/day}$ and $D = 0.003 \text{ m}^2/\text{day}$, respectively.

In typical bioremediation sites, the electron acceptor is injected in a contamination groundwater plume creating a favorable environment to occur contaminant biodegradation through the bacterial species naturally present in the medium. These three species are connected by means of this biological reaction ($\alpha_i = 1$, $i = 3, 4, 5$), and it is usual that the electron donor (contaminant) suffers sorption, which does not happen with the acceptor donor (oxygen) [Odenrantz, 1991]. Then, we simulate a contamination scenario, where a 5.0 mg/L background concentration of electron donor is initially in the system, with null Dirichlet and flux conditions.

Figures (1) and (2) compare the contaminant, electron acceptor and biomass concentrations snapshots in the presence of the sorption in non-equilibrium mode. Depending on the reaction constant values, K , the concentration behaviors are modified. The higher the value of the coefficient K , the higher is the contaminant (electron donor) plume retardation, as we can see comparing the dashed lines ($K = 10$) with the solid lines ($K = 0.1$). This result affects the electron acceptor and biomass behaviors. A higher retardation allows a bigger mixture area between the contaminant and the electron acceptor plumes, which encourages a rapid initial bacterial growth. In this way, we can see a biggest biomass growth for the initial times, represented by the dashed lines. However, this biomass growth leads to a greatest variation in the electron acceptor curve, observed at 15 days. The electron acceptor concentration in contact with the contaminant abruptly decreases, since it is consumed by the bacterial metabolism. On the other hand, the biomass quantity reduction again encourages the mixing of electron donor and acceptor and this allows a posterior biomass growth, which is not as emphasized as the initial growth. This nonuniform behavior can be also noted by the variation of shape and spacing between the contaminant profiles. When we assume $K = 0.1$, this variation is less stressed. In addition, comparing Figures (1) and (2), we also observe that in the linear case ($p = 1.0$), the retardation effect is bigger than the nonlinear one ($p = 0.75$). This reflects in the plume position as well as in the concentration values. Another important aspect is the fact that for higher values of K , both sorption conditions are almost coincident, as we can see in Figure (2). This also happened for the linear case [Couto and Malta, 2005] and allowed us to validate our results, comparing them with those published by Odencrantz [1991]. The non-equilibrium sorption case with $K = 10.0$ was compared with equilibrium results obtained by Odencrantz [1991] and they showed good agreement.

Figure (4) presents the snapshots for the linear and nonlinear cases, taking into account a mixing of both sorption conditions with the reaction constant $K = 0.5$. We clearly note that the equilibrium and non-equilibrium effects are accumulated, which leads to stronger behaviors than those described above for Figures (1) and (2). Again, we note that the retardation effects are bigger for the linear case than for the nonlinear one. Considering just a linear mathematical model, this result could determine an overestimate prediction on the contaminant plume position. From the nonlinear cases of Figures (3) and (4), we also can see that the effect added by the non-equilibrium sorption mode was sufficient to modify the contaminant, electron acceptor and biomass profiles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we examined in detail nonlinear sorption effects suffered by the electron donor in a multiple species contaminant transport system undergoing multiplicative Monod biodegradation kinetic. A new operator splitting approach was proposed to solve the nonlinear mathematical model. The numerical simulations corroborate the well-known observation that to better predict contamination scenarios the nonlinear physical and biological processes should be inserted in the model. Thus, the numerical methodology proposed here allowed to deal with all these nonlinearities together and could also be easily extend to multidimensional contaminant transport problems.

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FIGURE 1. Linear case ($p = 1.0$): comparison among electron donor (C_1), electron acceptor (C_2) and biomass (b_1) concentration profiles. Sorption in non-equilibrium mode with $K = 0.1$ (solid line) and with $K = 10$ (dashed line).

FIGURE 2. Nonlinear case ($p = 0.75$): comparison among electron donor (C_1), electron acceptor (C_2) and biomass (b_1) concentration profiles. Sorption in non-equilibrium mode with $K = 0.1$ (solid line) and with $K = 10$ (dashed line).

FIGURE 3. Nonlinear case: comparison among electron donor (C_1), electron acceptor (C_2) and biomass (b_1) concentration profiles. Sorption in non-equilibrium ($K = 10$) mode (solid line) and equilibrium mode (dashed line).

FIGURE 4. Electron donor (C_1), electron acceptor (C_2) and biomass (b_1). Sorption in equilibrium mixed with non-equilibrium ($K=0.5$) mode. Linear (solid line) and non-linear (dashed line) cases.